

Urea supergranules (USG) produced significantly higher yields (3.9 t/ha) than the other N sources (see table). Yields with split-applied urea and sulfur-coated

urea were similar, and significantly higher than with urea at transplanting. Yields varied from 2.3 to 4.4 t/ha. USG

performed best at 40 kg N/ha, but at higher N levels was as effective as split-applied urea and sulfur-coated urea. \mathcal{L}

Residual effect of three N sources and application rates on irrigated lowland rices

A. Buntan, C. J. S. Momuat, and I. T. Corpuz, Maros Research Institute for Food Crops (MORIF), Maros, South Sulawesi, Indonesia

Much of the available information on residual effects of N fertilizers is from studies conducted on upland or nonsubmerged soils. N fertilizer behavior in lowland or submerged conditions is distinctly different.

We studied the residual effects of N on irrigated wetland rice in an experiment after the International Network on Soil Fertility and Fertilizer Evaluation for Rice (INSFFER) trial. Soil was a plinthic Vertic Tropaquept, fine clayey, nonacid, and isohyperthermic at Maros, South Sulawesi, Indonesia. IR30 was planted. Treatments of the previous experiment are in the table.

During vegetative growth, there were no distinct visual differences among the treatments. Grain yield, panicles/m², percent filled grains, 100-grain weight,

Grain yield, yield components, and soil pH as affected by residual N from 3 sources at 3 rates on irrigated lowland rice, Maros, Indonesia.

N rate (kg/ha)	Previous treatment ^a		Grain yield (t/ha)	Productive tillers/m ²	Filled grain (%)	100 grain wt (g)	Height (cm)	soil pH at harvest
	Source	Method						
29	Control		3.7	248	90	2.0	72	5.8
	U	2/3 AP, 1/3 PI	3.5	216	91	2.0	67	5.9
	SCU	BI, AP	3.8	237	90	2.0	70	5.9
	USG	Hand placed 10-12 cm deep	3.8	255	90	2.0	71	5.9
58	U	2/3 AP, 1/3PI	4.3	263	91	2.0	72	5.9
	SCU	BI, AP	3.6	254	92	2.0	71	5.9
	USG	Hand placed 10-12 cm deep	3.3	235	90	1.9	68	6.0
87	U	2/3 AP, 1/3 PI	3.9	262	91	1.9	70	5.8
	SCU	BI, AP	4.2	263	92	2.0	75	5.9
	USG	Hand placed 10-12 cm deep	3.6	226	91	2.0	69	5.9
116	U	2/3 AP, 1/3 PI	3.6	228	90	1.9	71	6.0
	SCU	BI, AP	4.3	249	91	2.0	75	5.9
	USG	Hand placed 10-12 cm deep	3.8	258	91	2.0	74	5.9
Test of significance			ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns
CV (%)			16.2	12.6	10.8	8.6	12.0	10.0

^a U = urea, SCU = sulfur-coated urea, USG = urea supergranule, AP = at planting, PI = panicle initiation, and BI = broadcast and incorporated.

plant height at harvest, and soil pH at harvest indicated no significant differences among the treatments (see table). Even at the highest application

rate (116 kg N/ha), urea, sulfur-coated urea, and urea supergranules had no carry-over effect on the following rice crop. \mathcal{L}

A simple solution to sulfur deficiency, and an extension technique

C. J. S. Momuat, A. Buntan, S. Andyantoro, and I. T. Corpuz, Maros Research Institute for Food Crops (MORIF), Maros, South Sulawesi, Indonesia

In Apr 1983, a farmer leader from a barrio near MORIF came to the Institute with a problem. He had applied 2 bags of urea/ha 10 d earlier but plants had remained yellow and stunted.

We visited the field and identified S deficiency as the problem. Instead of telling the farmer to apply ammonium sulfate, we established a simple

Mean results of a simple experiment to solve sulfur deficiency in a farmer's field, South Sulawesi, Indonesia.

Parameter	Control	Urea	Ammonium sulfate	Urea + S	LSD (%)
Dry wt (g/5 hills) 30 d after fertilizer application	78	83	265	257	46
Plant ht (cm) at harvest	58	62	76	74	10
Panicles (no./m ²)	214	270	388	350	78
Spikelets (no./panicle)	92	102	116	108	ns
Filled grains (%)	84	85	86	86	ns
Grain weight (g/1000)	21	21	22	21	ns
Grain yield (t/ha), 14% moisture	2.5	3.0	5.0	4.8	0.85
Straw yield (t/ha), sun-dried	3.1	3.4	4.9	4.9	0.78
Maturity (days from planting to harvesting)	98	98	90	90	

experiment. Treatments were a control and applications of urea, ammonium sulfate, and urea + S to equal 100 kg N and 120 kg S/ ha. The experiment was in a Latin square. Establishing the plots was not difficult because rice was planted in rows at equal spacing. The fertilizers were broadcast on the surface when the rice was 30 d old.

Three days after fertilizer application,

the rice plants in the ammonium sulfate treatment were distinctly darker green than in the urea treatment. Plants in the urea + S treatment turned green 7 d after application.

Three days after the problem was reported, it was identified and a solution was provided — applying 100 kg ammonium sulfate/ ha. The farmer saw how ammonium sulfate, compared with

other treatments, dramatically improved the growth and development of his rice plants. There was a need, however, to point out that it was the S in ammonium sulfate that solved the problem. Both ammonium sulfate and S significantly increased IR50 yield, and shortened the period to crop maturity (see table). *ℳ*

Response of rice to phosphorus application methods

S.K. Saggur, M.S. Maskina, and O.P. Meelu, Punjab Agricultural University, Ludhiana 141004, India

We tested different methods of application to improve rice response to P fertilizer on light-textured soils. Soil was a loamy sand (Ustochrept) with pH 8.4, EC 0.20 mmho/cm, 0.23% organic C, and 6 kg Olsen's extractable P/ ha. Treatments were 13.1 kg P/ ha incorporated at last puddling, 13.1 kg P/ ha broadcast before transplanting, and a nursery root dip in 0.7% P slurry. N at 120 kg/ ha was applied in 3 equal

Effect of methods of P application on rice yield, Ludhiana, India.

splits and potash was applied at 13 kg K/ ha as a basal dose. Jaya seedlings aged 30 d were transplanted.

Grain yield was highest when P was incorporated at last puddling (see figure). Yields after the slurry treatment

were 150 kg/ ha less than the control, perhaps because of heat damage or chemical injury from the concentrated slurry. The slurry-treated plants wilted before transplanting and took more time than the normal seedlings to recover. *ℳ*

Effect of injured seedling roots on rice yield

M.S. Maskina, O.P. Meelu, and H.S. Baddesha, Punjab Agricultural University (PAU), Ludhiana 141004, India

Most rice grown in northern India is transplanted. Nurseries are grown using the wetland method. A fine, surface crust makes it difficult to uproot seedlings. Seedlings are uprooted manually, and because of the dense root mass and the crust, seedling roots often are damaged. Farmers think that root damage at transplanting reduces yields.

We studied the effect of seedling root damage on yields at the PAU Farm in 1982 and 1983. Treatments were:

- roots were handled carefully to avoid injury,
- roots were trimmed from the base of plants,
- 50% of the roots were removed, or
- all but 1 root was removed.

Effect of sodium, root injured on rice yield, Ludhiana, India.

Treatment	Grain yield (t/ ha)	N uptake (kg/ ha)
All roots	5.9	78
Trimmed roots	5.6	70
50% roots	5.8	74
1 root	5.7	68

Thirty-five-day-old seedlings were transplanted the second week of Jul. The crops received 120 kg N/ ha in equal splits at transplanting, 21 d after transplanting (DT), and 42 DT. PK at 13-12.5 kg/ ha were applied basally at transplanting. Soil was a loamy sand (Typic Ustochrept) with 5 mm percolation/ h, pH 8.5, EC 0.15 mmho/ cm, 0.23% organic C, and 0.06% total N.

Results (see table) showed that root injury did not affect grain yield. However, seedling N content and uptake were significantly lower when roots were trimmed at transplanting. *ℳ*

Yield response of IR32 to inorganic and organic fertilizers

R. le Cerff, R. Mufran, A. Buntan, and I. T. Corpuz, Maros Research Institute for Food Crops (MORIF), Maros, South Sulawesi, Indonesia

We studied the effect of applying NPKS as urea, TSP, KCl, and elemental S with rice straw, rice straw ash, rice hull ash, and carabao manure. Soil was a very fine, mixed, nonacid, isohyperthermic, alluvial Vertic Tropaquept. The surface 0-12 cm was clayey, with pH 6.5, 2.6% organic matter, 110 ppm available P (Olsen), CEC 32.0 meq/ 100 g, and 24.1,